

TRANSFORMATION OF THE COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH IN EDUCATION.

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Abstract: The article examines the problems of changing the content of education and didactic adaptation to the requirements of the new labor market in the formation of a competency-based approach.

Keywords: Competency-based approach, educational content, social flexibility of the labor market, didactic adjustment, human capital.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы изменения содержания образования и дидактической адаптации к требованиям нового рынка труда при формировании компетентностного подхода.

Ключевые слова: Компетентностный подход, образовательный контент, социальная гибкость рынка труда, дидактическая корректировка, человеческий капитал.

The transformation of the education system in our country in accordance with international requirements, the training of specialists capable of independent and logical thinking, mastering new techniques and technologies in production, and meeting the requirements of the international standard classification of education is considered a priority task of our education system. Today, the education system is aimed at the formation of new professional qualities such as the desire of the graduate to self-education, knowledge of new technologies and understanding of their possibilities of use, the ability to work in a team and independently. The formation of human capital, the formation of a person who has modern social and professional skills is considered an important condition of modern education. Because the requirements of the current labor market require the use of completely new working methods and methods to form qualified graduates in all important areas of production. The transition from a knowledge-based approach to a competency-based approach is a fundamental change in education. Since the 21st century, the formation of a competency-based approach has been implemented in the education system of developed countries. In organizing the educational process, the content of education is considered as the main component, since the goals and content of education are explained by the learning outcomes (Learning Outcomes) that the learner has mastered upon completion of a certain level of education. Learning Outcomes are understood as a specific set of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in the form of competencies as a component of human capital.

The quality of education is assessed on the basis of learning outcomes (Learning Outcomes) by means of the competence requirements of a graduate of any form of education or competencies reflected in educational standards. The main goal of introducing a competency-based approach to graduates in this transformation process is to increase the competitiveness of specialists based on the requirements of the labor market, change the content of education and update the educational environment. In this regard, the competency-based approach covers the following important tasks:

- the competency-based approach is considered as a fundamental tool for educational transformation;

- the competency approach reflects the requirements of the production sector and the international and local labor market;
- the competency approach is manifested as a modernization of the content of education in relation to the changing socio-economic realities of today's scientific and technological progress;
- innovative technological processes introduced into economic sectors, new technological jobs created in the areas of entrepreneurship and small business determine the relevance of the issue of the competency approach;
- the competency approach is manifested as a means of determining the correspondence of the knowledge, skills and experience of graduates to the level of complexity of the tasks they perform, the problems they solve, and the possession of professional skills;
- the competency approach is defined as an attribute of a specialist's readiness to engage in a certain activity or preparation for future professional activity;
- the competency approach is characterized by the ability to practically perform professional competence in conditions different from those in which this competence initially appeared. When approached from a didactic point of view, the competency approach performs the following tasks:
 - in determining the content of the educational process, the development of the graduate's acquired professional competences forms the ability to independently solve problems in various areas of activity;
 - is manifested as educational content, which represents the didactic adapted experience of solving problems in the educational process;
 - in organizing the educational process, it creates conditions for the formation of experience in independently solving cognitive, communicative, organizational, moral and other problems that make up the content of education;
 - the assessment of learning outcomes is carried out on the basis of an analysis of the level of mastery of education, to which the competency approach refers not as a knowledge-oriented component, but as a solution to practical activity problems and the fulfillment of the main functions of professional competence.

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